

SECOND ORDER LINES AND EXAMPLES OF IT

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Annotation : This in our article second orderly lines circle , ellipse , hyperbola , parabola, ellipse and hyperbola half arrows about thought my comments statement reported

Key words : Second orderly line white , circle , ellipse , hyperbola , parabola, ellipse and hyperbola half arrows , asymptote , joint hyperbola , canonical equation , symmetry center , symmetry axis , eccentricity , focus , directrix , parabola focus .

INTRODUCTION

Of geometry in development Central From Asia came out mathematicians Muhammad ibn Musa al- Khwarizmi , Abu Rayhan Beruni , Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abdurahman al- Khazini , Abul Vafo Buzmoni , Umar Khayyam , Mirza Ulugbek , Giyosiddin al- Kashi and of others service is large .

Seventeenth century french mathematician and philosopher Rene Descartes works due to , all mathematics , in particular geometry revolutionary again built coordinates method (method) of existence came _ Algebraic equations (inequalities) _ geometric images _ _ _ _ through interpretation to do and vice versa geometric issues solve analytic , formulas , equations systems using search opportunity appear did . Mathematics fanining new network analytical geometry to the body came _ Analytical geometry essence , geometric objects his algebraic (analytical) expression mos putting their _ properties to learn , to him mos algebraic expressions check through instead is increased .

The second orderly line and his equation . As you know , on the plane right line x and y variable coordinates relatively first degree was . Andy in the plane second orderly lines we learn . The second orderly lines x and y o ' zgaruvchi coordinates relatively second degree equation with represented by The second degree of the equation general appearance

$$Ax^2 + 2Bxy + Cy^2 + Dx + Ey + F = 0 \quad (1)$$

will be . (1) to the equation **second orderly of the line general equation** is called . Below certain cases , the second orderly lines analytical expressions find their _ properties we learn .

METHOD AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Circle and his equation . Definition . In the plain any $C(a, b)$ from the point teng away located points geometric O ' miga circle is called .

$M(x, y)$ circle appropriate optional point let (Figure 1). Circle definition according to CM distance it does not change distance R with let 's define

Figure 1

Figure 2

two point between distance find formula basically ,

$$CM = \sqrt{(x-a)^2 + (y-b)^2} \quad \text{ëku} \quad \sqrt{(x-a)^2 + (y-b)^2} = R$$

b O ' ladi .

Last of equality both side square ko ' tarib ,

$$(x - a)^2 + (y - b)^2 = R^2 \text{ (2)}$$

to the equation we will come To this equation center $C(a, b)$ point , radius R ga teng **circle canonical equation** called (2) and

$$x^2 - 2ax + a^2 + y^2 - 2by + b^2 = R^2 \text{ or}$$

$$x^2 + y^2 - 2ax - 2by + a^2 + b^2 - R^2 = 0$$

will be . This is the equation (1) $A=C, B=0$ which was private holidir . So , circle second orderly is a line .

Example 1. The second orderly line $x^2 + y^2 - 6x + 4y - 23 = 0$ equation with given b o ' lsin . His circle that show and center and radiusini toping .

Solution . x and y li hadlar on full squares we distinguish :

$$x^2 - 6x + 9 - 9 + y^2 + 4y + 4 - 4 - 23 = 0,$$

$$(x - 3)^2 + (y + 2)^2 - 9 - 4 - 23 = 0 \text{ or } (x - 3)^2 + (y + 2)^2 = 36$$

will be . It ' s a circle canonical is the equation . His center $C(3; -2)$, nu oq tada , radius $R = 6$ will be .

Ellipse and his equation . Definition . In the plain , each a from the point of view given two to the points which was distances sum unchanging from quantity consists of which was points geometric o ' rniga **ellipse is called** . Given points F_1 and F_2 get _ To these points ellipse tricks is called . Unchanged amount $2a$, tricks between distance $2c$ with defining coordinates _ system so we can OX read from tricks let it pass and coordinates head F_1F_2 distance in the middle let (Figure 2). $M(x, y)$ to the ellipse appropriate optional point if any _ according to

$$F_1M + F_2M = 2a \quad (3)$$

will be . As you know , $F_1 (+c; 0)$ and $F_2 (-c; 0)$ two __ point between distance find formula basically :

$$\sqrt{(x - c)^2 + (y - 0)^2} + \sqrt{(x + c)^2 + (y - 0)^2} = 2a$$

equation yield we do From this equation irrationality lose _

$$x^2 (a^2 - c)^2 + a^2 y^2 = a^2 (a^2 - c^2)$$

apparently we bring . $a^2 - c^2 = b^2$ with we define (because , $a > c$). In this case

$$\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{b^2} = 1 \quad (4)$$

equation yield we do (4) to the equation ellipse canonical equation is called .

Coordinates head , ellipse **symmetry center** , coordinates read **symmetry arrows** will be . $A_1 (-a, 0)$, $A_2 (a, 0)$, $B_1 (0, -b)$, $B_2 (0, +b)$

points ellipse tips , $a = OA_2$ ϵa $b = OB_2$ distances mos as **ellipse big and small half arrows** is called .

That's right so that the ellipse two symmetry axis , symmetry to the center has which was closed curves is a line .

$\epsilon = c/a < 1$ size ellipse eccentricity is called . Circle ellipse $a = b$, $\epsilon = 0$ which was private look at _ possible .

$M(x, y)$ from the point tricks which was distance ellipse focal radii called them _ r_1 and r_2 with if we define , $r_1 = a + \epsilon x$, $r_2 = a - \epsilon x$ will be .

Example $216x^2 + 25y^2 = 400$ ellipse half arrows , tricks and eccentricity toping .

Solution . Given equation 400 ga as ,

$$\frac{x^2}{25} + \frac{y^2}{16} = 1$$

apparently we bring . This from the equation $a^2 = 25$, $b^2 = 16$ and a half arrows mos as $a = 5$, $b = 4$ will be . It is known that $b^2 = a^2 - c^2$, as , $c^2 = 25 - 16 = 9$, $c = \pm 3$ will be . So , the tricks $F_1(3,0)$ and $F_2(-3,0)$ nu in white fibers will be . Eccentricity if , $\epsilon = \frac{c}{a} = \frac{3}{5}$.

Hyperbola and his equation . Definition . In the plain , each a from the point of view given up to two (focus) points which was distances separation unchanging from quantity consists of which was points geometric O ' rniga **hyperbola** is called (shown separation absolute value on taken , he tricks between remotely small and from 0 different).

Unchanged amount $2a$, tricks between distance $2c$ and coordinate arrows as in the ellipse take , $c^2 - a^2 = b^2$ mark enter _

$$\frac{x^2}{a^2} - \frac{y^2}{b^2} = 1 \tag{5}$$

equation yield we do (5) to the equation **hyperbola canonical** equation is called . Hyperbola tricks $F_1(+c; 0)$ and $F_2(-c; 0)$ (Figure 3) . Coordinates read **symmetry arrows** and coordinates head $0(0; 0)$ **symmetry** is the **center** . Hyperbola coordinate arrows $A_1(-a; 0)$ ϵa $A_2(a; 0)$ points cut off after that _ to the points **real tips** and $a = 0A_2$ distance **real half read** is called . $B_1(0, -b)$, ϵa $B_2(0, b)$ points hyperbola **abstract tips** , $b = 0B_2$ - **abstract half read** is called

Hyperbola two asymptotes has as its _ equations

$$y = \pm \frac{b}{a} x \tag{6}$$

will be .

$$\varepsilon = \frac{c}{a} > 1 \text{ to size } \underline{\text{hyperbola eccentricity}} \text{ deb}$$

called _

Hyperbola arrows $a = b$ if to him **teng sided hyperbola** is called and his equation

$$x^2 - y^2 = a^2$$

will be .

$$\frac{x^2}{a^2} - \frac{y^2}{b^2} = 1, \quad -\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{b^2} = 1$$

hyperbolas reciprocal joint called hyperbolas . _

Example $39x^2 - 16y^2 = 144$ hyperbola half arrows , tricks , eccentricity and aximptotes Find the equations .

Solution . Given tenlamani 144 ga become equation canonical

$$\frac{x^2}{16} - \frac{y^2}{9} = 1$$

apparently we bring . From this $a^2 = 16$, $b^2 = 9$ is real _ half bullet $a = 4$,

abstract half bullet $b = 3$ will be . $c^2 = a^2 + b^2$, $c^2 = 16 + 9$, $c = \pm 5$ tricks _

_ $F_1(+5; 0)$, $F_2(-5; 0)$ nu in white fibers will be . Eccentricity

$$\varepsilon = c / a = 5 / 4.$$

a and b of value (6) asymptote to the equation let go

$$y = \pm \frac{3}{4}x$$

equations yield we do

These are asymptotes is the equation .

Figure 3

Figure 4

Parabola and his equation . Definition . In the plain , each a from the point of view given to the point (focus) and given right to the line (direktrisa) distances reciprocal teng which was points geometric O ' rniga called a **parabola** .

Coordinates system so we can Ox read F (focus) and after DD_1 to the director perpendicular , Oy read esa focus and of the director in the middle pass (Figure 4). $M(x, y)$ parabolaga appropriate optional point get F from the point DD_1 right to the line which was distance p ($p > 0$) with we define Bunda $F(p/2, 0)$ as the director equation

$$x = -\frac{p}{2}$$

will be .

By definition basically , $MN = MF$. $N(-\frac{p}{2}, y)$

Two point between distance formula basically ,

$$x + p/2 = \sqrt{(x - p/2)^2 + y^2} .$$

From this equation irrationality lose _

$$y^2 = 2px \text{ Equation (7)}$$

yield we do These are abscesses to the axis symmetrical parabola canonical equation will be . Ordinates read **symmetry read** then the parabola equation

$$x^2 = 2py(p > 0)$$

apparently will be . This without $y = -p/2$ director equation , $F = (0; p/2)$ point focus (Figure 5) .

Figure 5

$M(x, y)$ from the point $F(p/2; 0)$ focus distance focal radius

is called and $r = x + p/2$. $M(x, y)$ from the point $F(0, p/2)$ focus

distance $r = y + p/2$ will be .

Example 4 $y^2 = 12x$ parabola focus and of the director Find $M(3; 6)$ the equation from the point focus which was distance determine .

Solution . Given equation (7) with compare $2p = 12$, henceforth $p = 6$, $p/2 = 3$. That's right so the focus $F(3; 0)$ at the point director equation

$x = -3$ we find . $M(3; 6)$ point for $x = 3$, is the radius of $r = 3 + 3 = 6$, $r = 6$
gravity will be .

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